

Deliverable

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D4.3 - Second example of content

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Disclaimer

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Statement of originality:

This document contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable describes the production and post-production process for pilot 2, with information on the material created and a roadmap for the subsequent pilots.

This document shows the creation process of the second pilot: pre-production (concepts, storyboards, script, casting), the shootings in Madrid, and the post-production process (scenario creation, editing, lighting, chroma cleaning, etc.).

The document includes the contents uploaded to Zenodo, orderly and classified. These contents correspond to the content, necessary for the demos and final pilot.

Different charts and tables of content includes a detailed description, images and links to the source where they are uploaded. All this information is required by the rest of the consortium to work in their different tasks for developing the second pilot and its technology.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
CoVR	Collaborative Virtual Reality
AR	Augmented Reality

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of this document

This deliverable shows the contents uploaded to Zenodo in relation to the second pilot of the VR-Together project. The purpose of this document is to present in a clear and orderly way:

1. The contents created in their different formats
2. The description of each content
3. The contents generated for the dissemination of the project
4. The description of each content

The following objectives are intended to be achieved:

- Easy access
- Clarity in the descriptions
- Generation of a useful guide
- Quick identification of the type of content that may be needed by each partner

1.2. Scope of this document

This document has been generated for internal use among the partners, in such a way that they can access the content. These contents have been created for the correct technological development and for the adequate diffusion of the works carried out under the project.

The scope of this document is public, with access allowed to all those who require it outside the consortium.

1.3. Status of this document

- Complete in terms of content, description and access links.
- Complete in terms of summary content tables.

1.4. Relation with other VR-Together activities

This document illustrates the content delivery for the second pilot and the development of the technology. The content here defined and ordered in different formats, users and characteristics, is the one used to make the demos that illustrate the second pilot. This content is the one that has been used to show the technological development. The contributions of this deliverable are then related to WP3 tasks, mainly T3.5. Testing, to WP4 tasks, in particular T4.2. Pilot Deployment and T4.3. Evaluation, and to WP5 tasks, in particular T5.2. Dissemination.

1.5. Deliverable content

The present deliverable includes a summarized view of the elaboration of content for the second pilot. It shows and illustrates each part of the process, from the conception of the idea to the expected release dates, including as well a first vision and expectations about what is coming for the following pilot. The post-production process is also included, step by step, illustrating the most important points.

The three pilots are inter-connected, telling and transmitting a story about a murder. The story developed focuses on the murder of Ms. Armova, a wealthy British lady, in unknown circumstances. Two persons were present at the time of the murder: Ryan Zeller and Christine

Gérard. The second pilot focuses the story days after the murder. A popular TV show host comments on this case, and the users can enjoy a live interview with the police officer in charge of this case.

To summarize, the utility of this deliverable is to have a complete and global vision of the work done for the second pilot and to understand how this work is planned and how it has led us to modify and improve the first ideas for the third pilot. This deliverable sums up and identifies all the contents and their access links. It is also important to point that the document collects the utilities of each generated file, for an efficient use of it. Figure 1 shows a graphical schedule of the upcoming pilots.

Figure 1. Work planning

2. CONTENT CREATION: PILOT 2

2.1. Introduction

In this second pilot of the VR-Together project, the story continues days after the end of the first interaction. The users are located in a new and modern TV set, where a news show is about to begin and to spill all the information about the case of the murder of Elena Armova. The users are part of the audience of the show, where they can see each other as part of the whole experience.

This second chapter will also need the cooperation of the users in terms of trying to understand what could happen between Elena Armova and the suspects. Just like in pilot 1, the experience presented by the VR-Together project allows to experience the sensation of togetherness in a virtual reality environment. However, and unlike the previous experience, all the users will experience and watch the same content.

This is the second of three pilots, where a thriller is told as an excuse to offer a unique and innovative virtual reality experience. The story behind the three episodes covers the investigation of the murder of Ms. Armova and all the details around it. For this purpose, a script was written and it is located in the section II of the annex. The script written features the following characters:

- GAVIN MICHAELS: TV host of Hearsay. He loves himself so much and he also wants to be the center of attention. Maria Espinoza and him share some kind of rivalry.
- HOWARD CHAPMAN: Enthusiastic expert about technology.
- MARIA ESPINOZA: TV reporter. Very talkative. She enjoys her job, however, there is a clear tension between her and Gavin Michaels.
- OFFICER PEARSON: Sarge substitute.
- SARGE HOFFSTETLER: A police inspector, aged, highly professional and strict rigor. His training and experience in murder cases has made him an excellent profiler. Know in a glance the weaknesses of the suspects and know how to respond to the questions to make mistakes and reach the truth.

The pilot 1 focused the story around a murder and both of the suspects of it. This second time the story takes place in two different locations: inside the TV set where the show Hearsay is recorded and the exterior of the building where Mrs. Armova was killed. The users will be transported from one place to another.

Figure 2 in section 2.2 represents the time schedule of all the tasks related to the pre-production, production and post-production of the second pilot.

2.2. Work planning

	MAR	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY
PRELIMINARY CONTENT DEVELOPMENT - PRE-PRODUCTION					
Definition of the production tasks of the second pilot	From the 1st	to the 30th			
Production details around the shooting	From the 1st	to the 30th			
Definition and guidelines of content. Start from the work from previous months. Concretion	From the 1st	to the 30th			
Elaboration of Script and review	From the 11th	to the 30th			
Script review and casting selection		From the 30th	to the 17th		
Shooting planning			From the 6th		
Script reading and rehearsal			May 18th		
PRODUCTION					
Shooting			May 25th and June 23rd		
POST-PRODUCTION					
Material preparation and removal from discs.			From May 27th		
Scripts updating after shooting. Compilation of camera parts, filming data, etc.			May 27th to the 29th		
Editing and conforming			From the 29th		Ongoing
Chroma cleaning, Unity scenario creation			From the 29th		Ongoing
CGI of the elements, masks, lighting and integration			From the 29th		Ongoing
Programming of the unity scenario			From the 29th		Ongoing
Programming and 3D settings			From the 27th		Ongoing
Unity scenario last settings			From the 27th		Ongoing
Subtitles			From the 27th		Ongoing
Content delivery				Second week	
Zenodo upload				Second week	

Figure 2. Gantt graphic

2.3. Summary of the planning and development over time

Following the plot of the first pilot, we wanted to continue this crime and police story, developing in time a scenario where more characters were involved and, at the same time, increasing the technological complexity of the project. After several meetings with the partners, Entropy Studio proposed this continuation of the story, relating as well with the police theme of the first part.

One of the objectives of the second pilot was to show the technological improvement in terms of telling a story within a virtual reality environment. In the first pilot, the user was a participant in the show thanks to an elaborated plot. In this second pilot, the users can experiment a brand new way of enjoying TV shows, where the environment changes quickly, moving the interest point from one location to another. The main characteristic about pilot 2 was the need of represent the content within a Live CoVR environment. The mandatory characteristics that the pilot needed were the following:

- The system needed to accept more than 2 end-users (they could be in different rooms and locations).
- In terms of facial expressions, it was needed to see enough details in the end-user and character representation.
- The system needed to be able to produce multi-source immersive content.
- Lastly, the system needed to be able to deliver a photorealistic live immersive VR environment.

Since the beginning of the year, the creative partners had a visual interpretation of what the pilot 2 could be. Some ideas were presented to the rest of the partners, not only to get an approval, but also to test technologically these ideas. The inspiration of the plot of the second pilot comes from different weather TV shows, where augmented reality (AR) is used in order to explain the details to the audience. This idea is shown in the following figure.

Figure 3. Example of content

The whole idea of the pilot 2 takes the user to the day after the crime scene of Ms. Armova. News run across the channels and the user is taken to a TV show where they meet other users and the host. The whole TV show can be visually interpreted as a mix between a news show

and a talent/contest show. The TV set is a shared space between the host and the users, being the first one in the center, leaving the outside circle to the users. Another characteristic of the second pilot is the live recording/broadcasting activity, that will happen at least once. Figures 3 and 4 shows a visual reference of what the set of pilot 2 might look like. The selection of the scenarios and formats were previously analyzed within the consortium, and it is discussed in D2.2

Figure 4. Example of content

In the last days of April, a final script was developed, and the casting process started. Meanwhile, in April and the first weeks of May, the pre-production process started as well. Some promotional videos were made as well to promote the whole project and the pilots.

We wanted to count on the same actor to play the role of Sarge, since he is the main character of the first pilot and he is in charge of the investigation of the death of Ms. Armova. However, due to schedule issues, he couldn't be present on the first day of shooting (May 25th), that is why we looked for another actor to play his role. A second shooting day was planned on June 23rd, to record this part. The shooting was located in two different places: BlueBerry Studios and LoomHouse, both places in Madrid. We decided to split the shooting since we needed an interior location to film the TV show segment. To record the police interview we used the exterior locations of LoomHouse to simulate a British street.

From that point on, Entropy Studio started the pre-production of the second pilot, taking care of the following tasks:

- Development of the script

- Contacting with casting companies and selection process
- Casting actors in Madrid
- Searching and selecting professionals for the following tasks:
 - Sound
 - Lighting
 - Stylism
- Script readings and modifications.
- Rehearsals with actors in Madrid.
- Pre-production of the shooting: required documentation (camera details, recruitment, etc.) and travel organization for the Entropy crew.

After the two shootings (on May 25th and on June 23rd), Entropy Studio began to work with the recorded material. The post-production work were scheduled for the months of June and July.

2.4. Pilot 2 plot

Gavin Michaels is the TV host of Hearsay, one of the most popular shows on TV. Hearsay is a news show-esque that informs users about news events. Particularly, pilot 2 focuses on an edition where Gavin introduces the death of Ms. Armova. She is a celebrity that was murdered the night before.

Users appear on a set that is similar to a TV contest/magazine show. On this show, the host talks to the users, in a simulated interaction. Gavin asks some questions about what is trending, so this gives the feeling that he is talking directly to the users. The users answer to the host as if they were a real person, but they are indeed, actors. The host says hello to the new audience and introduces the topic of Armova's death.

In that moment, the host makes a live connection with the TV reporter, near the murder scene, trying to get any information about the case. At some point, the environment starts to fade and transforms into the murder scene, thanks to a full 3D reconstruction.

The TV reporter describes that two suspects have been interrogated at the police station. One of them was the boyfriend of the victim, and the other one was her personal assistant. The user does not have more information. That is the moment where a police officer appears behind her, and the TV reporter takes the opportunity to talk to him, asking him questions that the audience already knows because of the interaction of the first pilot.

At some point in the conversation, the TV reporter brings up the possibility of the use of a new AI technology that can recreate anyone's personality through videos and personal recordings. She asks the police officer if they are going to use this brand new technology to clarify the murder of Ms. Armova. The police officer feels uneasy about sharing new details about the case. Figure 5 shows part of the un-recreated shoot scene.

Figure 5. Scene recorded

2.5. Casting

The casting process started in April. We were looking for three actors to play the different roles of the play: 1 TV host, 1 officer and 1 TV reporter. Because of schedule issues, Jonathan Mellor could not play his previous Sarge role in May, so we decided to look for another actor to play the role of the officer. We also decided to add up a little role of “technology nerd” into the first part of the act, played by David Comrie, who also played the role of Officer on May. In June, Jonathan Mellor played his previous Sarge role. Verónica Polo played the TV reporter in both months. Ana Revilla, Fernando Pérez, Guillermo Calahorra and Elena Garcinuño played an extra role to give the piece more credibility. Table 1 summarizes the selected actors and their played role.

	<p>Jimmy Shaw</p>	<p>Gavin Michaels</p>
	<p>David Comrie</p>	<p>Howard Champman</p>
	<p>Jonathan Mellor</p>	<p>Sarge</p>
	<p>David Comrie</p>	<p>Officer</p>
	<p>Verónica Polo</p>	<p>Maria Espinoza</p>

Table 1. Actors selected and their role

2.6. Shooting details and post-production

The technical specifications about the tools used to shoot the pilot in Madrid are summarized in the tables 2 and 3.

Interior shooting

Camera used	Z Cam K1
Obturation	1/120
Camera height	160cm.
File format	NTSC
Video format	2880P30(1:1)
ISO	100

Table 2. Interior shooting details

Exterior shooting (May 25th)

Camera used	Z Cam K1
Obturation	1/140
Camera height	154cm.
File format	NTSC
Video format	2880P30(1:1)
ISO	100

Table 3. Exterior shooting details (May 25th)

Table 4 summarizes the technical specifications of the second part of the shooting on June 23rd.

Exterior shooting (June 23rd)

Camera used	Z Cam K1
Obturation	1/120
Camera height	156cm.
File format	NTSC
Video format	2880P30(1:1)
ISO	100

Table 4. Exterior shooting details (June 23rd)

The annex includes more information about the shooting, like the calls for filming and its planning. Figure 6 shows some pictures of the shooting days.

Figure 6. Pictures from the shooting

2.6.1. Shooting details

As stated before, the shooting was divided into 2 days: May 25th and June 23rd. There was a reason behind this: the unavailability of Jonathan D. Mellor to play his previous role of Sarge in May 25th. We wanted to keep the continuity between pilots, so we wanted to count with the same actors.

First shooting: May 25th

May 25th was the first date to shoot the pilot. We decided to separate the shooting into two time slots: interior and exterior. The interior part corresponds to the scene where the TV show is presented, and the exterior scene corresponds to the interview of the Sarge/Officer by the TV reporter.

To record the interior part we shot at the Blueberry Studios, in Madrid. The shooting lasted about 5 hours (from 9AM to 2PM) and we recorded all the scenes where Gavin Michaels and Howard Chapman had text. Both parts were recorded with a chroma key behind them. However, we used a green one to shoot the part of Gavin and a yellow one to record the part of Howard. This is because the part of Howard was supposed to be on a screen, since he is telling some technical details and he is not the main host of the show.

Second shooting: June 23rd

On June 23rd the second part of the shooting took place. This time, Jonathan D. Mellor was part of the cast, playing the same role as in the first pilot. Since the role of the police officer only appears in the second part of the act, it was only needed to re-shoot this last section. That means that it was only an exterior shooting.

The shooting took place at Loom House Madrid, the same place as in May 25th. Since the technical crew already knew the location, the preparation of the set was a quick process. After a couple of rehearsals, the shooting started. Because of the sun position, the shooting could not start until, approximately, 7:30PM.

2.6.2. Post-production process

The following paragraphs summarize the post-production process of the second pilot.

After having everything shot, the post-production team started to prepare the TV scenario, where Gavin Michaels hosts the show. In this set, real and fake users are present (see Figure 7). The preparation and elaboration of this TV set on Unity took several weeks.

Figure 7. Unity screenshot

The team tried to find a solution for what we need, this is, a place for:

- up to four users
- a presenter
- an appearing window with a commentator
- a semi-sphere for displaying the 180 degrees stereo video of the reporter in the street

So, after studying many TV Sets we found that almost everyone of them uses a cylindrical shape.

The set was modelled with Autodesk Maya and then exported in FBX format to Unity.

It is divided in two parts, one is the static part where the users and the presenter are located, and the second part is animated. Once the presenter introduces the reporter, this part of the scenario unfolds with an animation, letting us see most of the semi-sphere where the video is displaying. Figure 8 represents the recreation of the TV set.

Once the action outdoors ends, this part comes back to its original state and the presenter keeps talking until the end.

Figure 8. Recreation of the TV set

The lighting in this Unity scene is part static and part dynamic. The part of the set that doesn't change, uses lightmaps to bake all the light and optimize the scene, but the part that unfolds and therefore is dynamic, uses dynamic lighting and doesn't have any light information baked.

The set uses some post-process effects that helps with the realistic look. Some of them are:

- Ambient Occlusion
 - Helps with the integration of the elements adding some dark corners in the intersections
- Chromatic aberration
 - Adds some vintage effect by separating Red, Green and Blue a bit.
- Anti-aliasing
 - Removes the jagged border effect
- Color Correction
 - Equalize the scene colors

2.6.3. Modifications and implementations

This content will be updated throughout the testing phase of the pilot. Some changes should be made, both to the videos and to the geometry in the Unity scene.

2.7. Content delivered

Table 5 summarize the uploaded contents including the data sets of the material developed and uploaded to Zenodo. It is an organized summary of what is specified below. It contains a brief description, the owner, and the final use of the different versions in a very summarized way to visualize in a first glance. All these contents belong to the second pilot of the VR Together project.

	Description	Corresponding pilot	Content owner	Type
Presenter_With_Audio.mp4	Zenodo ID: 10.5281/zenodo.3264940 https://zenodo.org/record/3264940	Pilot 2	VRT	Video
Reporter_With_Audio.MOV	Zenodo ID: 10.5281/zenodo.3264970 https://zenodo.org/record/3264970	Pilot 2	VRT	Video
Howard_With_Audio.mp4	Zenodo ID: 10.5281/zenodo.3265029 https://zenodo.org/record/3265029	Pilot 2	VRT	Video
VRTogether Pilot 2 TV Set Geometry Unity package	Zenodo ID: 10.5281/zenodo.3265039 https://zenodo.org/record/3265039	Pilot 2	VRT	Unity Package

Table 5. Data sets uploaded

2.8. Content delivered: Description of contents uploaded to Zenodo

This section lists all the content uploaded to the server Zenodo, detailing their characteristics. These tables shows a more detailed description of the contents in section 2.2.

All the tables (see Tables 6, 7, 8 and 9) contain the following information:

- File name
- Content description
- Package description
- Purpose
- File size
- Format
- Thumbnail: a little image to illustrate the content uploaded
- Link of the content

2.8.1. Uploaded content 1

File name	Presenter_With_Audio.mp4
Content description	Video of the presenter in stereo format and green background for real-time background removal.
Package description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Codec: H264 - MPEG-4 AVC • Dimensions: 1040x600 • Framerate: 29.97 fps • Bitrate: 13500kbps • Audio: Stereo 48000 kHz
Purpose	Video for Unity Client
File size	541.3 MB
Format	MP4
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/3264940

Table 6. Uploaded content

2.8.2. Uploaded content 2

File name	Reporter_With_Audio.MOV
Content description	Video of the reporter in stereo format 180°.
Package description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Codec: H264 - MPEG-4 AVC ● Dimensions: 5760x2880 ● Framerate: 29.97 fps ● Bitrate: 8805kbps ● Audio: Stereo 48000 kHz
Purpose	Video for Unity Client
File size	159 Mb
Format	.MOV
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/3264970

Table 7. Uploaded content

2.8.3. Uploaded content 3

File name	Howard_With_Audio.mp4
Content description	Video of the news anchor in stereo format.
Package description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Codec: H264 - MPEG-4 AVC ● Dimensions: 1536x768 ● Framerate: 30 fps ● Bitrate: 3579kbps ● Audio: Stereo 48000 kHz
Purpose	Video for Unity Client
File size	28 Mb
Format	.MP4

Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/3265029

Table 8. Uploaded content

2.8.4. Uploaded content 4

File name	VRTogether Pilot 2 TV Set Geometry Unity package
Content description	Unity package containing the TV set scene where all the pilot 2 happens.
Package description	Unity package containing all the geometry in FBX format, audio in MP3 format, animations and placeholders for the user, presenter, comentator and outdoor action.
Purpose	Unity scene to alocate all the assets
File size	16.8 Mb
Format	.unitpackage
Thumbnail	
Link	https://zenodo.org/record/3265039

Table 9. Uploaded content

3. CONTENT CREATION: PILOT 3

This section is out of the scope of the current document version.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The objectives and the summary of this year during the development of the second Pilot are:

1. Creation of high quality content following the story of the first pilot, achieving the following:
 - a. Recording a 5-6 minute story about a TV show in which different users see themselves in the TV set where the show is being recorded.
 - b. An avant-garde technology that allows us to visualize ourselves in real time while we watch the story and see others users enjoying the experience at the same time.
 - c. A content and a 3D environment creation of hyper-realistic quality.
2. Creation of a story that allows the correct visualization of the technology developed and its presentation in different festivals and fairs in the sector. This technology development includes the achievement of real-time elements (the representation of the live presenter), scalability goals (up to 4 users) and multi-source contents (such as remote users, mixture of volumetric users, billboard host, 180° video and 3D environmental TV set).
3. Definition and specification of the lines of action for Pilot 3 through different calls and a General Assembly meeting on June 12th in Barcelona, in which the current points were defined.

During the second year of the project we managed to continue creating and developing a fictional story started on the first year with the first pilot, which will be finished and it will be finished with the shooting of pilot 3 next year. The second pilot continues the story of the murder of Ms. Armova. The story developed focuses on the murder of Ms. Armova, a wealthy British lady, under unknown circumstances. This time, a famous TV show presents the latest news on the case, having the opportunity to talk to the police in charge of the investigation.

The final pilot, schedule for 2020, will conclude the presented story. Pilot 3 will face new technical and artistic requirements. The main concept about the last pilot is the idea about users being able to interact with objects and characters in the scene, driving the scenario through their interactions. Possible ways of interaction would include touching, gestures, gaze and speech. Characters will be fully 3D, with pre-recorded motion-captured scenarios. The plot and story for this pilot is being developed at this moment.

Finally, this deliverable had the following objectives:

GENERAL OBJECTIVES

1. To get a broad view of the content generated to support technological development and the different systems developed.
2. To get a broad view of the contents generated for the dissemination of the project.
3. To get an easily and quickly identification of each file.
4. To order of the files.
5. To help the general evaluation of the second phase of the project.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To showcase all the content recorded for the second pilot of the project.
2. To discover the following steps in order to start developing the third and last pilot.
3. To identify files and the technological development structure.

4. To help the general evaluation of the second phase of the contents for the second pilot and its dissemination.

ANNEX I - SCRIPT

INT. TV STUDIO - DAY

OFFICER SCRIPT

Our host GAVIN stands in the middle of the flashy, hi-tech studio, facing seated audience members on one side, while screens dance with various graphics behind him. Five USERS (and FAKE USERS) are arranged in a semicircle around him at the edge of a slightly raised area. The actual users occupy spaces 2 and 4 in the semicircle.

GAVIN

Welcome back, ladies and gents, to this special edition of "Hearsay". I'm Gavin Michaels. Shocking news out of London today as we learned of the death of hotel maven and society darling, Elena Armova. Did you all hear about this?

USERS (AND FAKE USERS)

Yes... terrible... couldn't believe it... (etc.)

GAVIN

Police are being very tight-lipped about this case, refusing to comment on cause of death or even if they suspect foul play. What do you think?

He turns to FAKE USER 1-

FAKE USER 1

Yeah... it would be pretty unusual for someone so young and healthy to just drop dead like that.

Gavin turns to FAKE USER 2 (in spot 3)-

GAVIN

Do you agree?

FAKE USER 2

Foul play, for sure.

GAVIN

What are your most pressing questions about this case?

FAKE USER 3

How much money did Zeller stand lose because of Armova?

GAVIN

Good question... speaks to motive. Any more?

FAKE USER 2

Why did Christine Gerard, the assistant, lie about her wrist wound? She's gotta be guilty of something.

GAVIN

We'll see if we can get any more info out of the police. ...So have you all heard about this new technology that interrogators can use? They

take security footage, news recordings, personal videos... everything a person has ever recorded... and then they feed it into an artificial intelligence program that can then recreate someone's personality? Let's talk to Howard Champman.

HOWARD

It's pretty cutting edge. This would allow police to actually interview the victim herself. It would be fascinating to see if they're planning to use the technology in this case...

GAVIN

...Thank you Howard. And now to answer all our burning questions, we have our correspondent on the scene in Mayfair, Maria Espinoza...

Gavin turns and the screen behind him switches to the street in front of Armova's apartment building, where MARIA stands holding a microphone.

MARIA

That's right, Gavin. I'm Maria Espinoza, reporter here. Police have been in and out of Miss Armova's building all day...

GAVIN

Maria, our audience wants to know what's happening with suspects Ryan Zeller and Christine Gerard. They both seem to have something to hide.

MARIA

Yes, despite the police silence
around this case, rumors are
flying. Ah, it looks like someone
is coming out now, yes...

She moves toward the police tape by the front door,
where SARGE (from Video 1) is exiting the building.

As she does so, the audience is immediately
transported to the street in front of Armova's
apartment, now watching the scene as if they are right
there.

MARIA (CONT'D)

I'm going to see if I can speak
with the officer who's just come
out...

Raising her hand and shouting-

MARIA (CONT'D)

Excuse me... officer...

The Officer stops with an annoyed huff, but appears
willing to be interviewed.

MARIA (CONT'D)

With whom am I speaking?

OFFICER

Officer Pearson, Metropolitan
Police Service.

MARIA

Officer, what can you tell us
about the death of Elena Armova?
Was this murder?

OFFICER

I'm afraid I can't comment on an ongoing investigation. You'll have to wait for the press briefing like everyone else...

MARIA

But Officer, our viewers have questions...

(turning toward camera)

GAVIN

Officer, do you think Ryan Zeller killed Armova?

The Officer pauses for a moment, choosing his words carefully.

OFFICER

I'm afraid I can't comment on anything or anyone related to this case...

MARIA

Is Zeller in custody?

Officer turns and walks toward his car as Maria follows, doggedly.

OFFICER

I'm sorry, no comment.

MARIA

...What about Christine Gerard, Miss Armova's assistant?

Officer stops for a moment.

MARIA (CONT'D)

Miss Gerard visited the
victim the night of the
murder and has an
unexplained injury, what can
you tell us about that?

Officer turns, an accusatory eye for the persistent
reporter.

OFFICER

Where did you get your information?

MARIA

Miss Gerard is rarely far from
Miss Armova's side. Her
absence from the public eye
over the last twenty-four
hours is suspect, to say the
least. Wouldn't you agree?

OFFICER

I am unable to comment at this
time.

MARIA

Will the police be employing
their controversial new AI
technology in this case? Will
you be interviewing Armova
herself?

Officer turns back toward her, thoughtful for a moment.

OFFICER

Since Miss Armova was such a public

figure, that is an option.

(MORE)

OFFICER (CONT'D)

I'm afraid I can't say any more than that. Now if you'll excuse me...

Officer tips his hat and exits the scene. Maria turns back to the camera with a shrug.

MARIA

There you have it, Gavin. Police are refusing to comment on the two individuals with the closest ties to Armova. However, Officer Pearson did confirm that AI technology may be used to help solve this crime.

Our world once again becomes the TV studio, with Maria and the street scene on a screen behind the hosts.

GAVIN

Very interesting, Maria, thank you.

He turns back to the Users.

GAVIN (CONT'D)

Well, audience, was it the boyfriend, Zeller? The assistant, Gerard? Was it suicide? A botched robbery? A drug overdose? What do you think?

FAKE USER 2

It would be nice to get in that
apartment and have a look around.

GAVIN

Yes, and I bet you'd love to
hear from Armova herself,
wouldn't you? That might
answer a few questions.
Well, ladies and gents,
that's our program for
today. Be sure to tune in
next time to see me and for
more on this story, and all
the news you just can't stop
talking about, on the next
edition of... "Hearsay".

I'm Gavin Michaels...

Closing titles swirl, music fades as the studio goes dark.

THE END

INT. TV STUDIO - DAY**SERGEANT SCRIPT**

Our host GAVIN stands in the middle of the flashy, hi-tech studio, facing seated audience members on one side, while screens dance with various graphics behind him. Five USERS (and FAKE USERS) are arranged in a semicircle around him at the edge of a slightly raised area. The actual users occupy spaces 2 and 4 in the semicircle.

GAVIN

Welcome back, ladies and gents, to this special edition of "Hearsay". I'm Gavin Michaels. Shocking news out of London today as we learned of the death of hotel maven and society darling, Elena Armova. Did you all hear about this?

USERS (AND FAKE USERS)

Yes... terrible...
couldn't believe it... (etc.)

GAVIN

Police are being very tight-lipped about this case, refusing to comment on cause of death or even if they suspect foul play. What do you think?

He turns to FAKE USER 1-

FAKE USER 1

Yeah... it would be pretty unusual for someone so young and healthy to just drop dead like that.

Gavin turns to FAKE USER 2 (in spot 3)-

GAVIN

Do you agree?

FAKE USER 2

Foul play, for sure.

GAVIN

What are your most pressing
questions about this case?

FAKE USER 3

How much money did Zeller stand
lose because of Armova?

GAVIN

Good question... speaks to motive.
Any more?

FAKE USER 2

Why did Christine Gerard, the
assistant, lie about her wrist
wound? She's gotta be guilty of
something.

GAVIN

We'll see if we can get any
more info out of the police.
...So have you all heard about
this new technology that
interrogators can use? They
take security footage, news
recordings, personal videos...
everything a person has ever

recorded... and then they feed it into an artificial intelligence program that can then recreate someone's personality? Let's talk to Howard Champman.

HOWARD

It's pretty cutting edge. This would allow police to actually interview the victim herself. It would be fascinating to see if they're planning to use the technology in this case...

GAVIN

...Thank you Howard. And now to answer all our burning questions, we have our correspondent on the scene in Mayfair, Maria Espinoza...

Gavin turns and the screen behind him switches to the street in front of Armova's apartment building, where MARIA stands holding a microphone.

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That's right, Gavin. I'm Maria Espinoza, reporter here. Police have been in and out of Miss Armova's building all day...

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Maria, our audience wants to know what's happening with suspects Ryan Zeller and Christine Gerard. They both seem to have something to hide.

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around this case, rumors are
flying. Ah, it looks like someone
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MARIA (CONT'D)

I'm going to see if I can speak
with the officer who's just come
out...

Raising her hand and shouting-

MARIA (CONT'D)

Excuse me... officer...

The Sarge stops with an annoyed huff, but appears
willing to be interviewed.

MARIA (CONT'D)

With whom am I speaking?

SARGE

Sergeant Hoffstetler, Metropolitan
Police Service.

MARIA

Sergeant, what can you tell us

about the death of Elena Armova?
Was this murder?

SARGE

I'm afraid I can't comment on
an ongoing investigation.
You'll have to wait for the
press briefing like everyone
else...

MARIA

But Sergeant, our viewers have
questions...
(turning toward camera)

GAVIN

Sergeant, do you think Ryan
Zeller killed Armova?

The Sarge pauses for a moment, choosing his words carefully.

SARGE

I'm afraid I can't comment
on anything or anyone
related to this case...

MARIA

Is Zeller in custody?

Sarge turns and walks toward his car as Maria
follows, doggedly.

SARGE

I'm sorry, no comment.

MARIA

...What about Christine Gerard,
Miss Armova's assistant?

Sarge stops for a moment.

MARIA (CONT'D)

Miss Gerard visited the
victim the night of the
murder and has an
unexplained injury, what can
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Sarge turns, an accusatory eye for the persistent reporter.

SARGE

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MARIA

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SARGE

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time.

MARIA

Will the police be employing
their controversial new AI
technology in this case? Will
you be interviewing Armova
herself?

Sarge turns back toward her, thoughtful for a moment.

SARGE

Since Miss Armova was such a public figure, that is an option.

(MORE)

SARGE (CONT'D)

I'm afraid I can't say any more than that. Now if you'll excuse me...

Sarge tips his hat and exits the scene. Maria turns back to the camera with a shrug.

MARIA

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today. Be sure to tune in
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the news you just can't stop
talking about, on the next
edition of... "Hearsay".

I'm Gavin Michaels...

Closing titles swirl, music fades as the studio goes dark.

THE END

ANNEX II - CALL FOR FILMING

Información de contacto
DIRECCIÓN: Ignacio Lacosta.
646 97 65 79
PRODUCCIÓN: Ana Revilla.
639 30 63 94
PRODUCCIÓN: Guillermo Calahorra.
644 05 91 38

Piloto #2
Orden de rodaje
Sábado, 25 de mayo de 2019

HORARIO DE RODAJE 09:00-21:00 **LISTOS A LAS** 10:00

COMIDA 14:30

LOCALIZACIÓN MAÑANA: Blueberry Studios. Pl. del Conde del Valle de Súchil, 19, 28015 Madrid ([Enlace en Google Maps](#))

LOCALIZACIÓN TARDE: Loom Tapices. Calle Vandergoten, 1, 28014 Madrid ([Enlace en Google Maps](#))

PREVISIÓN METEOROLÓGICA

sáb.	Soleado
	Máxima: 24°C
24° 9°	Mínima: 9°C
	Precipitaciones: 0%
	Salida de sol: 6:51, Puesta de sol: 21:28

Hospital más cercano:

- Localización mañana: Hospital Universitario HM Madrid (Pl. del Conde del Valle de Súchil, 16, 28015 Madrid, [enlace](#))
- Localización tarde: Hospital General Universitario Gregorio Marañón (Calle del Dr. Esquerdo, 46, 28007 Madrid, [enlace](#))

Estaciones de transporte público cercanas:

- Localización mañana: Quevedo (línea 2), San Bernardo (líneas 2 y 4), Bilbao (líneas 1 y 4)
- Localización tarde: Menéndez Pelayo (línea 1)

La comida será en *Mesón Restaurante EL SEGOVIANO* ([Enlace a Google Maps](#))

EQUIPO TÉCNICO

EQUIPO DE ACTORES

<p>DIRECTOR. Ignacio Lacosta PRODUCCIÓN EJECUTIVA. Ana Revilla PRODUCCIÓN. Guillermo Calahorra PRODUCCIÓN. Margarita Mansilla PRODUCCIÓN. Sergio Berzal PRODUCCIÓN. Fernanda Zaragoza SUPERVISOR VFX. Ignacio Lacosta DOP CÁMARA. Ignacio Lacosta MUA & STYLIST. Alejandra García TÉCNICO SONIDO. Rubén Durán GAFFER. Beñat Belaza</p>	<p>ACTRIZ. Verónica Polo ACTOR. James Carrol ACTOR. David Comrie ACTOR. Ana Revilla ACTOR. Fernando Pérez ACTOR. Guillermo Calahorra / Elena</p>
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CITACIÓN EQUIPO TÉCNICO

DIRECTOR	Ignacio Lacosta	09:00	PRODUCCIÓN EJECUTIVA	Ana Revilla	09:00
GAFFER	Beñat Belaza	09:00	PRODUCCIÓN	Guillermo Calahorra	09:00
VESTUARIO	Alejandra García	09:00	PRODUCCIÓN	Margarita Mansilla	08:45
SONIDO	Rubén Durán	10:00	PRODUCCIÓN	Sergio Berzal	08:45
			PRODUCCIÓN	Fernanda Zaragoza	08:45

CITACIÓN EQUIPO DE ACTORES

PERSONAJE	ACTOR	EN SET	MAQ-EST.	SET
GAVIN	James Shaw	09:15	09:30	10:00
OFFICER	David Comrie	09:15	09:30	10:00
MARIA	Verónica Polo	10:00	10:15	10:30
EXTRA (Policía)	Ana Revilla	17:00	17:15	17:30
EXTRA (Forense 1)	Fernando Pérez	17:00	17:15	17:30
EXTRA (Forense 2)	Guillermo Calahorra / Elena	17:00	17:15	17:30

NECESIDADES GENERALES	
CATERING	
ARTE: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Sirena- Luces azules / rojas- Cinta policia	VESTUARIO: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Gavin- Maria- Officer- Extra (Policia)- Extra (Forense 1)- Extra (Forense 2)
CÁMARA: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Palio- HDMI	PRODUCCIÓN: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Discos duros backup- Ordenador- Cesión de derechos- Parte de horas

Información de contacto
DIRECCIÓN: Ignacio Lacosta.
 646 97 65 79
PRODUCCIÓN: Ana Revilla.
 639 30 63 94
PRODUCCIÓN: Guillermo Calahorra.
 644 05 91 38

Piloto #2

Orden de rodaje

Domingo, 23 de junio de 2019

HORARIO DE RODAJE 17:00-21:00 **LISTOS A LAS** 19:00

LOCALIZACIÓN: Loom Tapices. Calle Vandergoten, 1, 28014 Madrid ([Enlace en Google Maps](#))

PREVISIÓN METEOROLÓGICA

dom. Sol y nubes
 Máxima: 29°C
 Mínima: 16°C
 Precipitaciones: 0%
 Salida de sol: 6:46, Puesta de sol: 21:49

29° 16°

Hospital más cercano:

- Hospital General Universitario Gregorio Marañón (Calle del Dr. Esquerdo, 46, 28007 Madrid, [enlace](#))

Estaciones de transporte público cercanas:

- Localización tarde: Menéndez Pelayo (línea 1)

EQUIPO TÉCNICO

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PRODUCCIÓN. Sergio Berzal
PRODUCCIÓN. Fernanda Zaragoza
SUPERVISOR VFX. Ignacio Lacosta
DOP CÁMARA. Ignacio Lacosta
MUA & STYLIST. Alejandra García
TÉCNICO SONIDO. Rubén Durán
GAFFER. Beñat Belaza

ACTRIZ. Verónica Polo
ACTOR. Jonathan Mellor
ACTRIZ. Ana Revilla
ACTOR. Guillermo Calahorra
ACTOR. ---